

When 3 to 4 mm long anther calluses were subcultured in auxin-free regeneration medium, plantlets formed within 15 to 20 days, and were albino or normal. Of the calluses plated from ASD8/Amaravathi, 16% produced green plants, and ASD8/Bagavathi formed 22% green plants. ASD8/Vaigai produced only albinos and ASD8/Zhinjan regenerated only roots (Table 2). □

Table 2. Regeneration of plants from anther calluses of Tamil Nadu Agricultural University rices, 1980.

cross	Anther calluses subcultured (no.)	Green plantlets (%)	Albinos (%)	Roots alone (%)	No differentiation (%)
ASD8/Vaigai (F ₁)	40	—	25	48	27
ASD8/Amaravathi (F ₁)	72	16	—	64	20
ASD8/Bagavathi (F ₂)	90	22	—	49	29
ASD8/Zhinjan (F ₁)	24	—	—	68	32

Pest management and control DISEASES

Effect of slow-release nitrogen fertilizers on rice brown spot disease

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Brown spot (BS) *Helminthosporium oryzae* Breda de Haan is becoming a serious disease of high yielding rice varieties in Tamil Nadu. Heavy nitrogen fertilizer application increases BS incidence.

A field trial in kuruvai (Jul-Oct) with the short-duration (105–110 day) variety TKM9 measured the effect of slow-release nitrogen fertilizer on BS incidence. Commercial urea, sulfur-coated urea, and urea supergranule (1-g size) were applied at 29, 58, 87, and 110 kg N/ha in a randomized

Effect of different forms of urea on BS incidence in rice.

Treatment	Disease intensity ^a at nitrogen levels				
	0	29 kg N/ha	58 kg N/ha	87 kg N/ha	110 kg N/ha
Commercial urea	—	5.1	5.0	4.6	5.0
Sulfur-coated urea	—	4.7	2.4	2.9	1.9
Urea supergranule	—	4.0	4.3	2.7	3.3
No nitrogen	5.6	—	—	—	—

^aBased on 1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice. Least significant difference at 5% level = 1.4.

block design with 3 replications. Urea was applied in two equal split doses: at transplanting and panicle initiation. Sulfur-coated urea was incorporated at transplanting. Urea supergranule was spot applied, one granule for every 4 hills, 15 days after transplanting. Phosphorus and potassium were applied at 50 kg/ha to all plots. Disease incidence was assessed at growth stage 9, using the Standard

Evaluation System for Rice.

No application and heavy application of urea caused heavy BS incidence. Application of sulfur-coated urea or urea supergranule appreciably reduced disease incidence (see table). These two fertilizers can be applied at levels from 87 to 110 kg N/ha with good reduction in disease incidence. Sulfur-coated urea performed better than urea supergranule. □

Response of two rice varieties to *Rhynchosporium oryzae* infection.

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Earlier qualitative observations have indicated that in Sierra Leone narrow-leaf rice varieties were less affected by rice leaf scald fungus *Rhynchosporium oryzae* Hashioka & Yokogi than broadleaf varieties. During 1979 and 1980 wet seasons (May-Oct), field experiments compared the response of ROK 16 (broad-leaf) and PN623-3 (narrow-leaf) to *R. oryzae* infection either with or without benomyl fungicide. Experiments were at

Table 1. Response of 2 rice varieties to *Rhynchosporium oryzae* infection in Sierra Leone.^a

Experimental site	Treatment	Leaf area infected (%)	
		ROK16	PN623-3
<i>1979</i>			
Sendugu-NP	Benomyl	0.9	0.8
	Untreated	3.4*	2.8*
Makassa-NP	Benomyl	2.2	2.5
	Untreated	5.2*	4.2*
<i>1980</i>			
Masorie-NP	Benomyl	0.5	1.5
	Untreated	5.9	7.0
Sendugu-NP	Benomyl	0.4	0.3
	Untreated	1.6	1.3
Kenema-EP	Benomyl	0.1	0.1
	Untreated	0.2	0.3

^aValues are means from the 4 top leaves in 1979 and from the 3 top leaves in 1980. NP = Northern Province, within 8 km from RRS; EP = Eastern Province, 360 km from RRS. ROK16 and PN623-3 have broad-droopy and narrow-erect leaves, respectively. For 1979, *denotes significant difference between benomyl-treated and untreated values; differences between varieties are not significant, $P = 0.05$. For 1980, LSD ($P = 0.05$) are 1.2 (Masorie), 0.7 (Sendugu), 0.1 (Kenema). Untreated plants were artificially inoculated at Masorie.